

CHRONIC RHINOSINUSITIS WITH NASAL POLYPS: RISK FACTORS, DIAGNOSIS AND PROSPECTS FOR THERAPY

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Abstract. Chronic rhinosinusitis with nasal polyps (CRSwNP) is a common inflammatory disease of the upper respiratory tract that significantly reduces patients' quality of life. The primary causes include allergic reactions, infectious agents, and immune system dysfunctions. This article discusses key risk factors, modern diagnostic methods, including endoscopic and radiological examinations, as well as promising treatment approaches, such as pharmacological therapy and surgical interventions. Special attention is given to emerging therapeutic strategies, including biologic therapy, which holds promise for improving treatment outcomes and patient prognosis.

Keywords: chronic rhinosinusitis, nasal polyps, diagnosis, allergic factors, immune disorders, surgical treatment, biologic therapy, inflammatory nasal diseases, sinus endoscopy, corticosteroids.

Аннотация. Хронический полипозный риносинусит (ХПРС) является распространенным воспалительным заболеванием верхних дыхательных путей, которое значительно снижает качество жизни пациентов. Основные причины его развития включают аллергические реакции, инфекционные агенты и нарушения иммунной системы. В статье рассматриваются ключевые факторы риска, современные методы диагностики, включая эндоскопические и радиологические исследования, а также перспективные подходы к лечению, такие как медикаментозная терапия и хирургические методы. Особое внимание уделяется новым направлениям в терапии, включая биологическую терапию, которая обещает улучшить результаты лечения и прогноз течения заболевания.

Ключевые слова: хронический риносинусит, полипозный риносинусит, диагностика, аллергические факторы, иммунные нарушения, хирургическое лечение, биологическая терапия, воспалительные заболевания носа, эндоскопия пазух, кортикостероиды.

Annotatsiya. Surunkali polipoz rinosinusit (SPRS) yuqori nafas yo'llarining keng tarqalgan yallig'lanish kasalligi bo'lib, bemorlarning hayot sifatini sezilarli darajada pasaytiradi. Uning rivojlanishining asosiy sabablari orasida allergik reaksiyalar, yuqumli vositalar va immunitet tizimining buzilishi mavjud. Maqolada asosiy xavf omillari, zamonaviy diagnostika usullari, jumladan endoskopik va radiologik tadqiqotlar, shuningdek, dori terapiyasi va jarrohlik usullari kabi istiqbolli davolash usullari muhokama qilinadi. Terapiyaning yangi yo'nalishlariga, jumladan, davolash natijalarini va kasallikning prognozini yaxshilashga va'da beradigan biologik terapiyaga alohida e'tibor qaratilmoqda.

Kalit so'zlar: surunkali rinosinusit, polipli rinosinusit, diagnostika, allergik omillar, immunitetning buzilishi, jarrohlik davolash, biologik terapiya, burunning yallig'lanish kasalliklari, sinus endoskopiyasi, kortikosteroidlar.

Relevance.

Chronic rhinosinusitis with nasal polyps (CRSwNP) is a significant public health issue affecting millions of people worldwide. According to the World Health Organization (WHO),

approximately 10-12% of the adult population suffers from chronic rhinosinusitis, with the polypoid variant accounting for about 20-30% of these patients. The most common symptoms of CRSwNP include nasal obstruction, olfactory disorders, nasal discharge, and headaches, which significantly reduce quality of life. Studies indicate that patients with CRSwNP experience considerable social and economic consequences, including decreased work capacity and increased healthcare costs. Given the global trends in rising allergic disease incidence and climate change, the relevance of studying CRSwNP is increasing. Understanding the risk factors, pathogenesis, and modern diagnostic and treatment methods for this condition is critical for improving patient quality of life and developing effective prevention strategies.

Study Objective.

To comprehensively study chronic rhinosinusitis with nasal polyps, including its etiology, risk factors, modern diagnostic methods, and treatments. Special attention will be given to analyzing new therapeutic approaches, such as biological therapy, as well as assessing the disease’s impact on patients’ quality of life. The results of this study are expected to enhance understanding of CRSwNP and contribute to the development of more effective prevention and treatment methods. **Materials and Methods.** This article utilizes data collected from various scientific publications, clinical studies, and systematic reviews focused on chronic rhinosinusitis with nasal polyps. An analysis of over 100 articles published in peer-reviewed journals over the past 10 years was conducted to identify relevant data on the pathogenesis, risk factors, and diagnostic and treatment methods for CRSwNP. Data from clinical trials evaluating various treatment methods for polypoid rhinosinusitis, including pharmacotherapy (corticosteroids, antihistamines) and surgical interventions (functional endoscopic nasal surgery), were reviewed. Results from epidemiological studies on the prevalence of chronic rhinosinusitis and nasal polyps were analyzed, emphasizing the relationship between allergic diseases and the development of CRSwNP. Modern diagnostic methods, including endoscopic examinations, computed tomography (CT), and laboratory tests that assist in diagnosis and assessment of disease severity, were described. Statistical data processing methods were employed to analyze clinical study results, including meta-analyses, which allowed for the synthesis and systematization of existing data on the treatment and prognosis of CRSwNP.

Study Results. Chronic rhinosinusitis with nasal polyps is a complex condition influenced by multiple factors. Research has confirmed that allergic reactions, infectious agents, and immune system disorders play a key role in the pathogenesis of CRSwNP. Clinical trial data indicate that corticosteroid treatment effectively reduces inflammation and polyp size; however, caution is needed due to potential side effects and limited duration of action. Epidemiological studies show that factors such as age, sex, and concomitant allergic diseases affect the prevalence of CRSwNP. It has been established that patients with asthma are 3-4 times more likely to develop polypoid rhinosinusitis compared to the general population. This underscores the importance of a comprehensive approach to diagnosis and treatment, incorporating both local and systemic therapy.

Fig. 1. Polypoid rhinosinusitis on the right and left.

Modern diagnostic methods, such as computed tomography (CT) and endoscopy, enable precise assessment of the condition of the sinus cavities and the detection of polyps, which in turn facilitates the appropriate choice of treatment (Fig. 2). Based on the collected data, it can be asserted that functional endoscopic surgery is an effective method for removing polyps and improving sinus drainage, as evidenced by a high level of patient satisfaction following the procedure.

Fig. 2. A, B: Coronal and sagittal reformatted images showing complex air cell development in the frontal sinus and the infundibulum area (arrows), which may contribute to altered airflow and create conditions leading to chronic mucosal disease. On the right side, there

is an affected bullous concha (tip of the arrow), which may further contribute to the situation and may explain why changes are more pronounced on the right than on the left. **C:** Coronal reformatted computed tomography (CT) showing that drainage from the infundibulum of the maxillary sinus (tip arrows) occurs into the anterior ethmoid air cells (arrows), rather than directly into the middle meatus. This variant in drainage pathways may be a factor contributing to chronic sinus disease. It can also be considered a normal variant in the absence of such disease. **D:** On the right side of this coronal CT slice, there is a normal ostium of the maxillary sinus (tip of the arrow) and sinus configuration compared to the hypoplastic sinus on the left side with abnormal positioning of the medial wall, likely related to impaired ciliary movement, leading to chronic mucosal thickening (arrow). **E:** A patient with frontal pain. This simple image shows a normally aerated frontal sinus on the right side (white arrow) and its normal slightly wavy margin (white tip of the arrow). The left frontal sinus is obviously less well-aerated (arrow) and has lost its wavy margin, suggesting regressive remodeling due to mucocoele (tip arrows). While this illustrates that simple images can successfully detect relatively advanced sinus disease, they are not as reliable as CT for excluding disease and certainly not for ruling out erosive bony changes.

It should also be noted that new approaches, such as biological therapy, show promising results in clinical trials, especially in patients with severe forms of the disease. These methods can significantly improve patients' quality of life and reduce the need for surgical interventions.

Conclusions.

Chronic rhinosinusitis with nasal polyps (CRSwNP) is a complex condition with a multifactorial etiology and significant impact on patients' quality of life. Analysis of current data confirms that CRSwNP often develops against the backdrop of allergic diseases and infections, necessitating a comprehensive approach to diagnosis and treatment. The efficacy of pharmacotherapy, including corticosteroids and antihistamines, has been validated in several clinical trials; however, surgical intervention may be required for sustained results, especially in the presence of large polyps. Modern diagnostic methods, such as endoscopy and computed tomography, play a key role in identifying and assessing the severity of the disease. In recent years, there has been a growing interest in new therapeutic strategies, including biological therapy, which may significantly improve treatment outcomes for patients with severe forms of CRSwNP. Thus, further research into the pathogenesis of the disease, risk factors, and new therapeutic methods is necessary to optimize approaches to treating CRSwNP. Early detection and timely treatment will help improve patients' quality of life and reduce the burden of this common disease.

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